

2024 Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop

This is the form to register for the meeting, submit your abstract, and provide your input for the topics of discussion for the 2024 Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop. First, please enter your registration information, including what broad topics you prefer to discuss at the workshop. If you would like to submit an abstract, please also add your abstract information in the last section, including what topics the abstract most closely aligns with.

The due date for submitting abstracts and in-person attendance is March 29, 2024. Abstracts submitted after the due date may be considered as space allows. Virtual registration is open until Apr 30.

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

Registration section

Please complete this section to register for the 2024 Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop.

2. Please enter your name. *

3. Please enter your ORCID (orcid.org). If you do not have an ORCID, it is easy to create one!

4. Please enter your institution or affiliation. *

5. Do you have a NASA badge or NASA identity?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

6. Do you intend to attend the workshop virtually or in-person? *

Mark only one oval.

In-person

Virtually

Unsure

7. There will be a limited amount of funds to support travel for in-person attendees. If *
selected for attending in-person, do you need assistance with travel costs?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

N/A

8. Please choose up to three software categories that are most important to you. *

Check all that apply.

- Mission-related software
- Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)
- Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)
- Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)
- Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Software related to models and simulations (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)
- ML/AI codes
- General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)
- Infrastructure as code, and web or cloud applications
- High performance computing

9. Please choose the three software lifecycle stages that are most important to you. *

Check all that apply.

- Discovery vs acquisition vs collaboration for software
- Funding software effectively
- Designing/developing software
- Developing vs contributing to software
- When to choose open or closed software?
- Releasing software (e.g. the Software Release Authorization process)
- Maintaining software, confirming reproducibility/reusability
- Retiring software
- Building, fostering, and managing software communities and collaborations
- Security and supply chain risk management
- Complying with policies (e.g. NPR 7150, NASA policies, etc)
- Formulating and aligning with best practices and standards for software

10. If you have a topic idea that isn't covered by the questions above, please state it briefly here.

If you are submitting an abstract, please also fill out the following section. Otherwise, you may submit this form. Thank you for registering for the 2024 Software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate Workshop. We look forward to hearing your perspective at the workshop.

Abstract section

Abstracts submitted through this section after March 29 will be considered as possible, but space will be limited. Please prepare your work to be shared openly outside of NASA in a manner to be determined (e.g. Zenodo, STRIVES). Oral presentations and posters are possible. We welcome topical talks on the opportunities and challenges for software development for SMD and on suggestions for discussions sections on these topics. We also encourage posters on the software that you are working on so that it can be shared with others across NASA. Please answer the questions below to complete the abstract submission process. **All questions in this section are required for abstract submission.**

11. Please enter the title of your abstract here.

12. Please enter the text of your abstract here, limited to 200 words.

13. Please choose the software category that your abstract most closely aligns with.

Mark only one oval.

- Mission-related software
- Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)
- Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)
- Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)
- Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)
- ML/AI codes
- General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)
- Infrastructure as code, and web and cloud applications
- High performance computing

14. Please choose the software lifecycle stage that your abstract most closely aligns with.

Mark only one oval.

- Discovery vs acquisition vs collaboration for software
- Funding software effectively
- Designing/developing software
- Developing vs contributing to software
- When to choose open or closed software?
- Releasing software (e.g. the Software Release Authorization process)
- Maintaining software, confirming reproducibility/reusability
- Retiring software
- Building, fostering, and managing software communities and collaborations
- Security and supply chain risk management
- Complying with policies (e.g. NPR 7150, NASA policies, etc)
- Formulating and aligning with best practices and standards for software

15. Should the software category or lifecycle stage be considered the stronger association for your abstract?

Mark only one oval.

- Software category
- Lifecycle stage
- Either is fine

16. Please indicate your preference for either an oral presentation, discussion topic, or a poster format. Please note that very few abstracts will be selected as presentations, and lightning talks will be available for accepted poster abstracts. All presentations and posters must be made public before the workshop in a manner to be determined, so please prepare accordingly.

Mark only one oval.

- Oral preferred
- Poster with lightning talk preferred
- Discussion topic
- Any of the above

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms